

DIRECTIONS FOR ORGANIZING ACTIVITIES TO PREVENT THEFT BY PREVENTION INSPECTORS

Abdukarimov Sodiq Zokir ugli

Cadet of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14250271>

Theft is the most common form of property crime, and its low detection rate, coupled with its covert nature, makes it difficult to uncover. Additionally, existing and unresolved socio-economic problems in society negatively impact the effectiveness of preventing this crime. The object of theft prevention is social relations related to the protection of others' property. Therefore, in theft prevention, it is primarily important to increase the vigilance of individuals and legal entities who own property and to improve the protection of their assets. It should be noted that the activities of prevention inspectors are of great importance in organizing and implementing the prevention of theft crimes. Specifically, prevention inspectors are responsible officials for organizing and implementing comprehensive preventive measures to protect property and prevent embezzlement in enterprises, organizations, and institutions located in the administrative territories where they serve, as well as for citizens residing there. Of course, when organizing the activities of prevention inspectors in theft crime prevention, it is necessary to pay special attention to identifying and eliminating the causes of these crimes and the conditions that contribute to them.

Based on the analysis, the following main causes of theft crimes should be cited:

- socio-economic problems, i.e. unemployment of the majority of the population, shortcomings in supporting low-income families, including those in need of social protection;
- lack of spirituality, in particular, the presence of a segment of the population seeking easy money and wealth, as well as the formation of lighthearted individuals prone to easy living and playful laughter;
- the emergence of such vices as drug addiction and chronic alcoholism, the lack of the ability of this category of people to work hard and, as a result, the presence of a desire to earn money easily;
- shortcomings in the field of governance, in particular, the failure to take measures to provide employment for the population, the commission of corruption crimes by certain individuals in government bodies, etc.

It is also necessary to include victim behavior of victims, that is, it has been established that the majority of victims of theft left their property unattended or treated it with indifference, while in some cases they openly displayed their wealth to others.

Therefore, in the prevention of theft crimes, it is advisable not only to combat criminals but also to increase the vigilance of citizens, educate them on being attentive to their property and not leaving it unattended, and to carry out awareness campaigns in this direction. Furthermore, for the effective organization of theft crime prevention, it is crucial for prevention inspectors to analyze which types of thefts were previously committed in the administrative territory, where they occurred, and at what times of the day. Additionally, depending on the nature of the object of theft, the following types of theft crimes can be distinguished: theft committed in homes; livestock theft; street theft; theft from vehicles; vehicle theft; pickpocketing, that is, theft of money and items from pockets; and theft committed in stores and warehouses. Depending on the type of theft, the mechanism, time, and place of its commission differ from one another. Moreover, the latency of thefts is high, and some citizens do not report to law enforcement agencies, considering the stolen goods and items to be insignificant.

According to V.V. Luneev, the actual crime rate is several times higher than the number of crimes known to the justice system, and the crimes they are aware of are several times greater than the number of officially registered crimes.

Therefore, in the organization and implementation of theft prevention, prevention inspectors should organize and implement the following measures:

First, constantly monitor the lifestyle of individuals who have previously been prosecuted for theft offenses and are on preventive records in the service area, studying their close relationships;

Second, organize the installation of security alarms in multi-story buildings and apartments in cooperation with the National Guard and carry out awareness campaigns in this regard;

Third, regularly conduct educational work with citizens to prevent the abandonment of their livestock in rural areas;

Fourth, submit proposals to local government bodies on establishing paid parking facilities for vehicles;

Fifth, ensure complete evening lighting on streets and roads, submitting mandatory recommendations to "Elektrta'minot" enterprises to address shortcomings in this area;

Sixth, propose to the leadership the organization of new daytime and evening patrol routes in areas where theft is most frequent, particularly on streets, avenues, and other public places;

Seventh, form "Fidokor yoshlar" community patrol groups in the mahalla and effectively organize their activities; In conclusion, it should be noted that the activities of prevention inspectors are of great importance in preventing any type of crime, including theft, in the administrative territory where they serve. In particular, a deep analysis of the specifics of the region in organizing the prevention of theft, identifying the causes of these crimes and the conditions that allow them, ensures their timely elimination, and early prevention of theft crimes.

References:

1. Криминология. Махсус қисм: Дарслик / И. Исмаилов, Қ.Р. Абдурасулова ва бошқ. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИВ Академияси, 2015. – 744 б.
2. Кузнецова Н.Ф. Проблемы криминологической детерминации. – М., 1984. – С.44.
3. Лунеев В.В Преступность XX века. Мировые, региональны и российские тенденции. – М., 1997.–С.125

